

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of Co^{II} salicylates with N-donors

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Manuscript received 19 January 2004, revised 13 August 2004, accepted 11 April 2005

Co^{II} salicylate react with various N-donors in organic medium (ethanol) to give solid complexes having general formula $[M\{O_2C(OH)R\}_2]L_2$ where $R = C_6H_4$, $L = 3$ - and 4 -CNPY; α , β and γ -picolene; $3,4$ - and $3,5$ -lutidine and isoquinolene. Co^{II} salicylate forms oily complex with 2-CNPY, which did not give reproducible results. All the complexes are of 1 : 2 stoichiometry irrespective of the amount of the ligand added and have been shown by the physio-chemical methods to be mononuclear and possess a *trans*-distorted octahedral structure in which the salicylate group function as a bidentate chelating ligand through phenolic and carboxyl oxygens. All N-donor ligands co-ordinate through their N-atoms.

Complexes of Co^{II} carboxylates with various nitrogen donors have been investigated widely¹⁻⁸. These studies reveal that 1 : 1 addition complexes involving binuclear, carboxylate bridged structures, identical to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate, are formed preferably when the nitrogen donor is sterically hindered e.g. $[Co_2(O_2C(Ph)_2L)_2]$ ($L =$ quinolene)⁴, or when the carboxylate anion is strongly basic, e.g. $[Co_2(O_2C(But-t)_2L)_2]$ ($L =$ pyridine, 2-methylpyridine, 4-methylpyridine, quinolene and quinaldine)⁸.

A considerable amount of research work has been carried out on the preparation and characterization of transition metal complexes with N-donors like aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic amines on account of their diverse structural characteristics and uses. For example : 4-cyanopyridine complexes with $CoCl_2$ were tested for mutagenic activity in the test strains of *Salmonella typhimurium*⁹. Mixed ligand cobalt complex of the type $[Co(tpp)(NO_2)(4-CNPY)]$ ($tpp =$ tetraphenyl porphyrinato) are used as catalysts for the oxidation of triphenyl phosphine by molecular oxygen¹⁰.

Literature survey of the complexes of Co^{II} with N-donors indicated that as compared to the amount of work that has been carried out on the addition complexes of N-donors with various inorganic salts and carboxylates of Co^{II}, far less work has been done on the addition complexes of Co^{II} substituted and unsubstituted salicylates. In the present investigation synthesis and characterization of Co^{II} salicylate with various N-donors was taken with a view to investigate the structure of the complexes isolated and to discern the mode of binding of the cyanopyridine ligand which can function in more than one manner as a co-ordinating entity.

Experimental

Materials : Reagent grade chemicals were used as received. Solvents were purified prior to use following the literature procedures. The basic cobalt carbonate

$2CoCO_3 \cdot 3Co(OH)_2$ were repeatedly washed with hot water to remove any soluble impurity and dried. Ligands like 2-, 3- and 4-CNPY were used as such whereas α , β and γ -picolenes, 3,4- and 3,5-lutidine and isoquinolene were purified by fractional distillation after keeping them overnight over KOH pellets.

Synthesis of complexes : Co^{II} salicylate were isolated *in situ* of the reaction medium by refluxing basic $CoCO_3$ (1.29 g, 0.025 M) and salicylic acid (3 g, 0.02 M) in ethanol (120 ml). The refluxed solution was filtered while hot to remove unreacted carbonate and used as such to form various complexes by adding the appropriate ligands like [3-, 4-CNPY, α , β and γ -picolene, 3,4- and 3,5-lutidine and isoquinolene] in the proportions based on adduct likely to be isolated. The reaction mixture on concentration, cooling and crystallization gave the desired product (50–60%), which was separated recrystallised from methanol and dried in vacuum desiccator containing calcium chloride.

The CHN contents were determined micro analytically from the Punjab University, Chandigarh, molar conductance of the complexes were determined on their millimolar solutions in ethanol using a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter type CLOI/02A and conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.521. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were carried out at room temperature by Gouy's method in the Chemistry Department, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The solution spectra of the complexes in ethanol in the range 18625–18875 cm^{-1} , 200–400 nm on UV-265FS UV-Vis recording spectrophotometer and the IR spectra were recorded over the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} on nujol mulls using IR spectrophotometer at Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu. Biological studies were also carried out from R.R.L., Jammu. Thermal decomposition studies were carried out at the heating flow rate of 30 [ml/min] on a detector DTG at Department of Physics, Uni-

versity of Jammu, Jammu. The ESR spectra of the complexes were recorded at room temperature on FE-3 XG JEOL X-band instrument.

Results and discussion

The adducts of Co^{II} salicylates have been prepared with various N-donor ligands such as 3- and 4-CNPy, α , β and γ -picolones, 3,4- and 3,5-lutidine and isoquinoline. All the complexes obtained were of 1 : 2 stoichiometry irrespective of the amount of the ligand added. They are light pink to pink in color except purple in case of IQ. These complexes are stable in air and soluble in ethanol, methanol and other polar solvents (chloroform, nitrobenzene, dimethylformamide). Molar conductance of these complexes in $10^{-3} M$ solution in ethanol medium is of the order of 33–42 $\text{mol}^{-1} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$. These values are much less than the values 120–140 $\text{mol}^{-1} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ reported for uni-univalent electrolytes¹¹ suggesting that complexes under study are non-electrolytes in ethanol.

Cobalt(II) being a d^7 ion can have in an octahedral envi-

ronment either $t_2g^5eg^2$ or $t_2g^6eg^1$ electronic configuration for its ground state depending upon the field strength of the ligand involved. The magnetic values for high-spin Co^{II} octahedral complexes fall in the range of 3.87 and 5.20 B.M. However, the experimentally observed magnetic moments fall in the range 4.7–5.2 B.M. and the difference between the two values has been due to the variation in orbital contribution which in turn depends upon number of factors like ground state term, stereochemistry of the complex, spin-orbit coupling constant, ligand field strength (Dq), temperature independent para-magnetism^{12–16}.

Solution spectra of these complexes exhibit a main absorption band centered around 18625–18875 cm^{-1} which is assigned to a ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition showing that Co^{II} ion exists in an octahedral environment in these complexes.

The infrared spectra were recorded over the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} and important infrared spectral bands of the complexes along with their tentative assignments are given in Table 1. The important regions of absorptions fall in three

Table 1. Analytical, magnetic and electronic spectral data of Co^{II} salicylato complexes (N-donors)

Sl. no.	Adduct	Colour	Analysis (%) :				μ_{eff} b.m. at 294 K	Observed bands (cm^{-1}) $[{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)]$
			Calcd. (Found)					
			Co	C	H	N		
1.	Bis(salicylato)bis(3-cyanopyridine) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)_2]$	Pink	10.88 (10.85)	57.65 (56.25)	3.32 (3.01)	10.34 (10.01)	5.02	18675
2.	Bis(salicylato)bis(4-cyanopyridine) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)_2]$	Pink	10.88 (10.83)	57.65 (56.69)	3.32 (3.00)	10.34 (10.01)	5.08	18695
3.	Bis(salicylato)bis(α -picoline) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(\alpha\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]$	Pink	11.35 (11.32)	60.09 (59.06)	4.62 (4.03)	5.39 (5.12)	5.06	18650
4.	Bis(salicylato)bis(β -picoline) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(\beta\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]$	Pink	11.35 (11.31)	60.09 (59.12)	4.62 (4.01)	5.39 (5.00)	5.01	18685
5.	Bis(salicylato)bis(γ -picoline) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(\gamma\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]$	Pink	11.35 (11.32)	60.09 (58.99)	4.62 (3.99)	5.39 (4.99)	4.99	18625
6.	Bis(salicylato)bis(3,4-lutidine) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(3,4\text{-C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N})_2]$	Light pink	10.77 (10.73)	61.43 (60.23)	5.11 (5.00)	5.11 (5.00)	4.98	18600
7.	Bis(salicylato)bis(3,5-lutidine) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}[\text{Co}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO}\}_2$ $(3,5\text{-C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N})_2]$	Light pink	10.77 (10.72)	61.43 (61.01)	5.11 (5.01)	5.11 (5.01)	5.11	18670
8.	Bis(salicylato)bis (isoquinoline) Co^{II}	Purple	12.75	59.75	3.67	3.02	5.12	18672

groups : (i) 1600–1430 and 1230–990 cm⁻¹ for ligand vibrations, (ii) 1650–1600 and 1410–1380 cm⁻¹ for (COO) stretching vibrations, (iii) below 650 cm⁻¹ for ring deformation modes of the heterocyclic ligand and (Co–O) and (Co–N) stretching vibrations.

Previous studies have shown that 3- and 4-CNPpy coordinate with metal ions through the pyridine ring nitrogen only because $\nu(\text{CN})$ remains unchanged^{17–20}. In the free 3-cyanopyridine ligand C≡N stretching frequency fall at 2788, 2388 and 2332 cm⁻¹ and 2850, 2620 and 2240 cm⁻¹ in 4-CNPpy. Whereas in the present complexes these vibrations show the +ve shifts (Table 2). The absence of negative shifts in the C≡N stretching frequencies on co-ordination rule out the interaction of the cyano group with Co^{II} ion supporting coordination of the ligand through pyridine nitrogen which is further confirmed by observing negative shift C–H in out of plane deformation vibration. Since nitrile nitrogen is not used in co-ordination, it automatically shows that 3- and 4-CNPpy must use pyridine nitrogen for co-ordination, which is confirmed by observing C–H out of plane deformation vibration of 3- and 4-CNPpy which shows –ve shifts on co-ordination. The C≡N stretching frequency decreases in 4-

CNPpy while in the 3-CNPpy complexes a slight increase is observed for the C≡N stretching vibrations. This is assumed to be due to a resonance effect.

Infrared spectra of α , β and γ -picolene adducts of Co^{II} salicylates reveals that almost all of the bands originating from the co-ordinated picolines show positive shifts confirming that picolene co-ordinated via its N-atom^{21–24}. Similarly IR spectral data of other nitrogenous ligands support their co-ordination through nitrogen. The mode of bonding of the carboxylate group was previously gathered from COO stretching vibrations occurring in the range 1650–1600 and 1410–1350 cm⁻¹ because the COO stretching frequencies in carboxylate complexes are sensitive to co-ordination to a metal ion and are effected differently depending upon the mode of bonding of the carboxylate group^{25,26}. It is shown that $\Delta\nu$ values (frequency difference between asymmetric and symmetric COO stretching modes) for four major different types of carboxylate groups fall in the order : monodentate > bridging > bidentate > ionic. The presence of high frequency bands in the range 1590–1650 cm⁻¹ are considered to be diagnostic of unidentate coordinate. The high frequency band is due to acquiring enhanced double

Table 2. Significant infrared bands (cm⁻¹) of Co^{II} salicylate with N-donors

Sl. no.	Complex	Ligand vibrations		(C–H) in plane deformations	Ring vibrations	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ stretching
		C≡N stretching	C–C and C–N			
1.	3-CNPpy	2788, 2388, 2232,	1584, 1550, 1492, 1420,	1216, 1194,	1022,	440s, 640s
	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (3-C ₆ H ₄ N ₂) ₂]	2790, 2390, 2250	1595, 1564, 1500, 1440	1220, 1199	1030	
2.	4-CNPpy	2850, 2620, 2240,	1580, 1565, 1470, 1420,	1210, 1190,	1020,	400s, 540s
	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (4-C ₆ H ₄ N ₂) ₂]	2830, 2730, 2480	1590, 1585, 1480, 1450	1230, 1200	1040	
3.	Picolene	3040, 3000, 2940,	1970, 1810, 1650, 1580,	1420, 1240,	1130,	492s, 554m
	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (α -C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂]	3060, 3060, 2990	1990, 1850, 1670, 1590	1460, 1280	1160	
4.	[Co{C ₆ H ₇ (OH)COO} ₂ (β -C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂]	3078, 3060, 2995	1980, 1870, 1690, 1600	1470, 1290	1180	464s, 522m
	5.	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (γ -C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂]	3099, 3080, 3000	1990, 1890, 1700, 1660	1490, 1310	1200
6.	Lutidine	3090, 3040, 2960,	1990, 1860, 1660, 1590,	1450, 1260,	1150,	434m, 612s
	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (3,4-C ₇ H ₉ N) ₂]	4010, 3060, 2980	2000, 1880, 1670, 1600	1470, 1280	1172	
7.	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (3,5-C ₇ H ₉ N) ₂]	4025, 3066, 2990	2020, 1900, 1690, 1620	1485, 1290	1193	430m, 600s
	8.	Isoquinoline	3060, 2480, 2280,	1930, 1660, 1630, 1600,	1470, 1310,	1190,
	[Co{C ₆ H ₄ (OH)COO} ₂ (C ₉ H ₇ N) ₂]	3090, 2480, 2300	1960, 1660, 1590, 1560	1495, 1360	1200	

bond character by one of the C–O bond. The salicylate ion obtained through the abstraction of a proton from the carboxyl group is reported to function in its complexes as a uninegative anionic bidentate chelating ligand through phenolic and carboxyl oxygens^{28,29} (Fig. 1). The electron spin resonance spectra of Co salicylate with 3-cyanopyridine has

Fig. 1. Structure of bis-amine complexes of Co^{II} salicylate. M = Co^{II}, L = ligand and O⁻ = salicylate anion coordinating through phenolic and carboxyl oxygens.

been recorded and the line shape of its spectrum resembles the line shape of Co²⁺ in MgO at 4.2 K. (Fig. 2) [Rhombic-Compressed] which clearly demarcates that in these complexes Co^{II} is in distorted octahedral environment^{30–32}.

Fig. 2. First derivative ESR spectrum of Co²⁺ in MgO at 4.2 K.

The thermal analysis curve of the complex bis(salicylato) bis(γ -picolene) Co^{II} (Fig. 3) shows that the complex is stable up to 373 K and starts decomposing gradually. The DTA curve shows first endotherm at 436 K which completes at 477 K followed by the second endothermic peak at 521 K corresponding to the gradual loss of two molecules of salicylate and loss of 1/2 molecules of γ -picolene (wt. loss : calculated, 4.744 mg, 61.745%. Found : 4.769 mg, 62.064%). Before the second endotherm could establish an exotherm starts from 591 K and completes at 707 K corresponding to the abrupt loss of remaining γ -picolene molecules (wt. loss : calculated; 2.071 mg, 26.95%. Found : 2.03 mg, 26.418%). TGA curve indicates weight gain from 709 K up to 972 K resulting to the formation of Co₃O₄ as an end product.

Fig. 3. The thermal analysis curve of the complex bis(salicylato) bis(γ -picolene) Co^{II}.

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